

MICROSTRUCTURAL CHARACTERISATION OF 3-D WOVEN SiC/SiC-BASED COMPOSITES AFTER TENSILE TESTING AT ROOM AND ELEVATED TEMPERATURE IN DIFFERENT ATMOSPHERES

Ian J. Davies¹, Takashi Ishikawa¹, Masaki Shibuya², and Tetsuro Hirokawa³

¹*Airframe Division, National Aerospace Laboratory,
6-13-1 Ohsawa, Mitaka-Shi, Tokyo 181, Japan*

²*Corporate Research and Development, Ube Industries Ltd.,
1978-10 Kogushi, Ube-Shi, Yamaguchi 755, Japan*

³*Research and Development Department, Industrial Textile Division, Shikibo Ltd.,
1500-5 Shibahara-Minami, Yokaichi-Shi, Shiga 527, Japan*

SUMMARY: 3-D woven SiC/SiC-based composite consisting of surface-modified Si-Ti-C-O fibres and polymer conversion-derived matrix was tested in tension in vacuum (1200-1380°C) and air (1000-1200°C). In addition, several specimens were surface-sealed using a proprietary technique prior to mechanical testing. Resultant tensile property/strain curves are discussed together with fracture surface characteristics such as main failure mode and fibre pull-out length distribution. The effect of test condition on intra-fibre bundle spatial distribution of fibre fracture characteristics is also mentioned. Composite properties at room and elevated temperature in vacuum (unsealed) and air (surface-sealed) were generally consistent with a stable fibre/matrix interface. Unsealed specimens tested at elevated temperature in air exhibited properties consistent with extensive fibre/matrix interface oxidation.

KEYWORDS: microstructural characterisation, SiC/SiC, tensile test, stress/strain, fibre pull-out, fracture mirror

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) which have shown potential for use in high temperature structural applications include those based on the SiC/SiC system. These composites contain fibres with either Si-C-O or Si-Ti-C-O structures comprising of β -SiC nanoparticles partially surrounded by aromatic carbon layers in an amorphous SiO_xC_y matrix for the Si-C-O fibre and $\text{SiO}_x\text{C}_y\text{Ti}_z$ matrix for the Si-Ti-C-O fibre. Matrix densification is generally achieved using either chemical vapour infiltration (CVI) or polymer conversion (PC) techniques.

Significant research has been conducted into optimisation of the fibre/matrix interface which is known to significantly influence high temperature mechanical properties (particularly for oxidising atmospheres). The problem of high temperature fibre/matrix interface stability has also been addressed through coating or sealing the composite surface with an oxidation-resistant glass layer.

The present work is concerned mainly with mechanical and microstructural characterisation of a 3-D woven SiC/SiC-based composite (without an oxidation-resistant glass layer) after tensile testing in vacuum and air from room temperature (RT) up to 1380 °C. In addition, exploratory tests were also carried out on a limited number of specimens after the surface had been sealed with an oxidation-resistant glass compound.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The composite examined in this work utilised continuous Si-Ti-C-O fibres woven into an orthogonal 3-D configuration with fibre ratios in the x, y, and z directions being 1, 1, and 0.13, respectively and a fibre volume fraction estimated to be 40 %. The Si-Ti-C-O fibres (Tyranno LoxM) had been surface-modified to produce an outer 10 nm SiO_x-rich layer surrounding an inner 40 nm carbon-rich layer whilst matrix densification used the PC method and a precursor similar to polytitanocarboasilane (PTCS). After machining to a geometry suitable for tensile testing, a limited number of specimens were surface-sealed using a proprietary technique (Kawasaki Heavy Industries, Kakamigahara City, Japan).

Mechanical testing of unsealed specimens was carried out with the loading direction parallel to the specimen y-axis (experimental details being given elsewhere) at RT and also at elevated temperature in vacuum (1-3 Pa)(1200-1380 °C) and in air (1000-1200 °C). Surface-sealed specimens were tested in a similar configuration up to 1200 °C in air. It should be noted that tensile strain could not be accurately measured beyond 1300 °C in vacuum (limitation of the specimen grip) and also for unsealed specimens at elevated temperature in air.

Experimental stress/strain curves were characterised by computer fitting of a high-order polynomial curve after which the instantaneous tensile modulus, E, and cumulative damage energy could be derived. Cumulative damage energy (CDE) indicates the energy absorbed by the composite during failure and so may be used to qualitatively measure the “toughness” of the composite, with:

$$\text{Cumulative damage energy} = \frac{1}{b \cdot h \cdot L_o} \int_0^S F dA \quad (1)$$

where b is the mean initial test specimen width (m), h is the mean initial test specimen thickness (m), L_o is the specimen gauge length (m), F is the tensile force acting on the specimen (N), S is the composite failure strain, and A is the longitudinal elongation (m). The majority of energy absorbed during failure is known to result from fibre pull-out so that CDE may also provide information concerning fibre pull-out properties and hence the status of the fibre/matrix interface.

Microstructural observations to evaluate the general nature of the fracture surface were initially carried out using a zoom lens optical microscope (OM) (Olympus SZH) at low magnification (≤20). Additional investigation concerning the fracture surface in the composite zy-plane was carried out at higher magnification (~50) (Olympus STM5-BD). Fibre pull-out length distributions were determined using this technique through measuring the projection of fibre pull-out length in the zy-plane. Obscuration of fibres with small pull-out lengths behind those with larger pull-out lengths was minimised through considering only fibres which had

pulled-out nearest to the microscope lens. Fibre pull-out length distributions will also be examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) at a later date.

Preliminary examination of individual fibre fracture surfaces was carried out for selected specimens using SEM (JEOL JSM-6300F). In order to determine any spatial dependence of fibre fracture properties within fibre bundles, fibres were examined at the end and centre of the fibre bundle major axis for each specimen. In both cases the fibre bundle was scanned from edge to edge along its minor axis with all fibres within an approximate 100 μm “corridor” being analysed. A minimum of 100 fibres were analysed in each area with the relative position, fibre diameter, surface character, and fracture mirror size (if applicable) being measured for each fibre. Only initial results are presented here with a more complete analysis being given elsewhere.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mechanical Properties

Representative tensile property/strain curves for composites examined in this paper have been presented in Fig. 1. The unsealed composite exhibited excellent mechanical properties at RT with a tensile strength of 389 (+/-48) MPa (Fig. 2) and tensile strain to failure of 1.14 (+/-0.04) % (Fig. 3(a)). Such values, combined with a CDE of 2634(+/-340) kJm^{-3} (Fig. 3(b)) compare extremely favourably with those obtained for previous SiC/SiC-based composites and suggest the fibre/matrix interface to possess near-optimal properties. Tensile strength, σ , and modulus, E , values obtained from Fig. 1 were broadly similar to those predicted by modified Rule of Mixtures equations:

$$E = \eta_f E_f V_f + E_m V_m \quad (2a)$$

and

$$\sigma = \eta_f \sigma_f V_f + \sigma_m V_m \quad (2b)$$

where V is the volume fraction of the respective phase, η_f is the fibre orientation factor, and the subscripts f and m refer to fibre and matrix properties respectively, with the following assumptions:

The decrease in tensile modulus with increasing strain at small strain levels (≤ 0.2 %) was attributed to a reduced contribution from the matrix component (due to microcracking). The matrix in SiC/SiC-based composites is known to have a substantially lower tensile strain to failure (≈ 0.1 %) compared to that of the fibres (≈ 1 %).

Mechanical properties from $\varepsilon \approx 0.4$ % until just prior to failure were due almost entirely to fibre and fibre/matrix interface properties.

Following on from the previous assumption, the composite failed at a tensile strain similar to that of the fibres. However, the tensile strength of the composite was only 50 % of that predicted from Eqn. 2b (with $\sigma_m V_m \approx 0$). A large proportion of this difference may be attributed to fibre strength reduction upon inclusion in the composite whilst another factor in

the present case may be the non-alignment of fibres along the loading axis (due to the weaving procedure).

Fig. 1: Tensile property curves for unsealed and surface-sealed SiC/SiC-based composite: (a) stress/strain, and (b) modulus/strain

It should also be noted that the composite initial tensile modulus was determined by significant contributions from both fibre and matrix. This situation is different from the case of SiC/SiC-based composites with CVI-derived matrices where the majority of the initial tensile modulus contribution is due to the matrix.

Tensile properties were almost identical for unsealed composite at 1200 °C in vacuum as for the RT case (Figs. 1-3) apart from a slight reduction in initial tensile modulus (attributed to matrix degradation) indicating the fibre/matrix interface to be stable at 1200 °C in vacuum.

Further increases in test temperature for unsealed specimens in vacuum resulted in a 50 % decrease in tensile strength by 1380 °C (compared to RT and 1200 °C). A decrease in mechanical properties under these conditions would be expected as Si-Ti-C-O fibres are known to degrade at elevated temperature, even in vacuum. Thus, a decrease in composite mechanical properties under such conditions does not necessarily imply a degradation of the fibre/matrix interface.

Fig. 2: Tensile strength vs test condition for unsealed and surface-sealed SiC/SiC-based composite. Note non-linear temperature scale

Although strain measurement was not possible for unsealed composite at elevated temperature in air, qualitative observations indicated the tensile stress/strain curve to be approximately linear with a strain to failure of $<0.1\%$ and, as such, is consistent with mechanical property/strain data presented in Fig. 1 for unsealed composite tested at RT after ageing in air (1200 °C/100 hours). The implication is that mechanical properties of unsealed composite are significantly reduced by exposure to oxygen at elevated temperature and this is borne out by tensile strength data presented in Fig. 2. The exact mechanism for the reduction in mechanical properties under these conditions has not been established for the composite under investigation but would be consistent with oxidation of the fibre/matrix interface producing a substantial increase in interface sliding stress and transformation to notch-sensitive behaviour observed by previous authors. The fibre/matrix interface in the present composite is known to consist essentially of a carbon-rich layer which makes such a scenario likely.

Tensile property/strain curves for surface-sealed composite tested at elevated temperature in air have also been included in Fig. 1. Although it should be stressed that such data is preliminary, the curves appear similar to those of unsealed composite at elevated temperature in vacuum. Such a conclusion may also be inferred from comparison of respective tensile strength (Fig. 2), strain to failure (Fig. 3(a)), and CDE (Fig. 3(b)) data. It is suggested that surface-sealing of the specimen is effective in severely retarding oxidation of the fibre/matrix interface, at least for short-term exposure (in the order of several minutes). These results are also consistent with preliminary creep investigations (1100 °C in air) of surface-sealed composite which have shown typical lifetimes of 6×10^4 s at 200 MPa and may indicate that long-term exposure at elevated temperature in air is feasible for these materials.

Fig. 3: Parameters determined from tensile stress/strain curves of unsealed and surface-sealed SiC/SiC-based composite: (a) tensile strain to failure, and (b) cumulative damage energy. Note non-linear temperature scale

Microstructural Investigation

The composite tensile tested at RT exhibited a “brush-like” fracture surface (Fig. 4(a)) with extensive fibre pull-out characteristic of “tough” CMCs and reflected in the relatively high CDE values achieved (Fig. 3(b)). The primary crack path in the composite tested at RT followed the inter-fibre bundle porosity perpendicular to the loading axis, indicating such pores to be a preferred route for crack propagation under these conditions. A similar fracture mode was also observed in unsealed specimens tested at elevated temperature in vacuum and also for surface-sealed specimens tested at elevated temperature in air, indicating crack initiation and propagation to be similar for these cases.

In contrast to this, unsealed composite tested at elevated temperature in air possessed a relatively smooth fracture surface (Fig. 4(b)) with little evidence of fibre pull-out, indicating brittle failure to have occurred. As stated earlier, such a failure mode was attributed to oxidation of the fibre/matrix interface. The primary crack path in this case showed no preference for the inter-fibre bundle porosity and was consistent with crack initiation within a fibre bundle followed by catastrophic crack propagation.

Fig. 4: Optical micrographs illustrating fracture surfaces for unsealed SiC/SiC-based composite after tensile testing: (a) room temperature, and (b) 1200 °C in air

Fig. 5(a) illustrates the effect of test temperature on fibre pull-out length distribution for unsealed composite tensile tested in vacuum with the distributions being similar for the RT, 1200 °C, and 1350 °C cases. The shift in fibre pull-out length to smaller values at 1300 °C was attributed to a transient deterioration in vacuum condition during testing. Previous researchers found that exposure to oxygen at elevated temperature may increase the fibre/matrix interface sliding stress by an order of magnitude compared to that at RT and thus even a minor decrease in vacuum quality may have a noticeable effect on fibre/matrix interface-dependent properties. A bimodal fibre pull-out length distribution was noted for the composite when tested at 1380 °C with a transition point of approximately 370 μm . Although not fully understood at present, such a change in behaviour at 1380 °C would be consistent with changes in the Si-Ti-C-O fibre (and fibre/matrix interface) at this temperature.

Preliminary fibre pull-out length distributions for surface-sealed specimens tested in air (Fig. 5(b)) show the pull-out length range to be similar to that of the unsealed composite tested at RT and elevated temperature in vacuum (Fig. 5(a)). The general form of the distributions in Fig. 5(b) is uncertain but at least one specimen (1200 °C) bears a resemblance to those seen in Fig. 5(a). From mechanical property data presented earlier it would be reasonable to expect fibre pull-out distributions for surface-sealed specimens at elevated temperature in air to be similar to those of unsealed specimens in vacuum at the respective test temperature. Thus, the fibre pull-out length data appears to add weight to the unsealed specimen fibre/matrix interface being stable at elevated temperature in vacuum (at least up to 1350 °C) with similar behaviour probable for surface-sealed specimens at elevated temperature in air.

Preliminary fibre fracture surface characteristics of unsealed composite tested in air at RT, 1100 °C, and 1200 °C were examined using SEM. Fibre fracture surfaces could be characterised into two main groups (“rough fracture surface” (RFS) and “smooth fracture surface” (SFS)) with the RFS fibres being further sub-divided into three categories, i.e.,

- (i) rough fracture surface with a fracture mirror origin at the fibre surface (RFS-S),
- (ii) rough fracture surface with a fracture mirror origin within the fibre body (RFS-B),
- (iii) rough fracture surface with no obvious fracture mirror (RFS-N), and
- (iv) smooth fracture surface (SFS).

Fig. 5: Cumulative failure vs fibre pull-out length for SiC/SiC-based composite: (a) unsealed tested in vacuum, and (b) surface-sealed tested in air

Fig. 6 illustrates the fraction of fibres with different fracture surface characteristics as a function of test temperature and position with the fibre bundle for unsealed composite tested in air. Although not included in Fig. 6, the fraction of RFS-B fibres in all cases was almost insignificant compared to that of RFS-S fibres ($\leq 2\%$ for the RT specimen) and is consistent with results of previous researchers. It may also be observed that the percentage of SFS fibres was substantially larger at 1100 °C and 1200 °C compared to at RT. One explanation for the presence of SFS fibres is that they represent fibres with such low fracture strength that a fracture mirror boundary was not formed. However, the more likely scenario in the present case is of the fibre and matrix being so strongly bonded following exposure to oxygen at elevated temperature that the propagating crack passed from matrix to fibre with little or no

change in velocity or direction. Further evidence for such a scenario is that all SFS fibers possessed negligible fibre pull-out.

It was also noted that SFS fibres were preferentially positioned around the perimeter of the fibre bundle, i.e., not in the centre. This can be more clearly observed in Fig. 7(b) with SFS fibres being preferentially positioned towards lower and higher values of the fibre bundle minor axis (which corresponds to the outer edge of the fibre bundle). In contrast to this, RFS-S fibres appear mainly limited to the central portion of Figure 7(b) parallel to the major axis (which corresponds to the central region of the fibre bundle). If the SFS fibres were indeed due to oxidation of the fibre/matrix interface, as seems likely, then it would suggest oxygen to have infiltrating the fibre bundle from the outer surface. Such a proposition is in contrast to previous researchers who concluded that oxygen attacks the fibre/matrix interface along the length of individual fibres. One explanation for this difference may be that the narrow (40 nm) carbon-rich layer at the interface in the present composite allows rapid SiO₂ formation and so limits oxidation to the composite surface, i.e., self-healing behaviour .

Fig. 6: Fibre fracture characteristics at the centre and edge of a fibre bundle for unsealed SiC/SiC-based composite tensile tested in air. Note non-linear temperature scale

Fig. 7: Fibre fracture surface characteristics at the centre of a fibre bundle after tensile testing: (a) room temperature, and (b) 1100 °C in air

CONCLUSIONS

- (i) The main characteristics of tensile property/strain curves were found to be consistent with predictions obtained from the modified Rule of Mixtures equation together with several assumptions.
- (ii) At room temperature the composite exhibited extensive fibre pull-out with the main crack path following the inter-fibre bundle porosity. This was accompanied by excellent mechanical properties including a tensile strength of 389 (+/-48) MPa and strain to failure of 1.14 (+/-0.04) % and suggested the fibre/matrix interface to have near-optimal properties.
- (iii) Unsealed composite tested at 1200 °C in vacuum possessed similar mechanical properties (except initial tensile modulus) and fracture surface characteristics as for the room temperature case. Increasing the test temperature further resulted in similar fibre pull-out properties but decreased tensile strength (50 % at 1380 °C) compared to at room temperature. It was proposed that the fibre/matrix interface was stable up to at least 1350°C in vacuum.
- (iv) Unsealed composite tested in air at 1100 °C and 1200 °C had a relatively flat featureless fracture surface with little evidence of fibre pull-out. This was reflected in poor mechanical properties and attributed to oxidation of the fibre/matrix interface under such conditions.
- (v) Surface-sealed composite tested in air up to 1200 °C had similar mechanical, fracture surface, and (possibly) fibre pull-out properties as for the unsealed composite in vacuum. This indicated that the surface-sealant utilised was successful in dramatically reducing oxygen diffusion into the composite under these conditions.
- (vi) Most fibres in the composite tested at room temperature possessed “rough” fracture surfaces with well-defined fracture mirrors originating at the fibre surface (RFS-S). However, for the unsealed specimen tested in air at elevated temperature the majority of fibre fracture surfaces were “smooth” with no evidence of a fracture “mirror” (SFS) whilst RFS-S fibres were mainly limited to the central portion of the fibre bundle. These results suggested oxidation to have proceeded from the outer surface of the fibre bundle (as opposed to along the fibre/matrix interface of individual fibres).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by funding from the Science and Technology Agency of Japan whilst one of the authors (IJD) was supported as a Science and Technology Agency Fellow. The authors gratefully acknowledge Y. Nomura and N. Suzuki for help with mechanical testing.

REFERENCES

1. Bodet, R., Bourrat, X., Lamon, J., and Naslain, R., "Tensile creep behaviour of a silicon carbide-based fibre with low oxygen content", *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 30, 1995, pp. 661-677.
2. Bunsell, A. R., Berger, M. H., and Hochet, N., "Structural and mechanical characterisation of some alumina and SiC based fibres", *High-temperature ceramic-matrix composites II (A. G. Evans and R. Naslain, Ed.)*, *Ceramic Transactions*, volume 58, American Ceramic Society, Westerville, 1995, pp. 85-94.
3. Droillard, C., Voisard, P., Heibst, C., and Lamon, J., "Determination of fracture toughness in 2-D woven SiC matrix composites made by chemical vapor infiltration", *Journal of the American Ceramics Society*, Vol. 78, No. 5, 1995, pp. 1201-1211.
4. Ishikawa, T., Shibuya, M., Hirokawa, T., and Watanabe, N., "Mechanical properties of 3-D fabric ceramic composites using new PC type matrix for improved oxidation resistance", *Proceedings of the 37th JSASS/JSME structures conference, July 12th-14th, Fukuoka, Japan*, Japan Society of Aeronautical and Space Sciences, Tokyo, 1995, pp. 29-32 (in Japanese)
5. Naslain, R., "Challenging ceramic matrix composites for applications in severe environments", *Advanced Composite Materials*, Vol. 5, No. 1, 1995, pp. 35-44.
6. Masaki, S., Moriya, K., Yamamura, T., Shibuya, M., and Ohnabe, H., "Development of Si-Ti-C-O fiber reinforced SiC composites by chemical vapor infiltration and polymer impregnation and pyrolysis", *High-Temperature Ceramic-Matrix Composites II (A. G. Evans and R. Naslain, Ed.)*, *Ceramic Transactions volume 58*, American Ceramic Society, Westerville, OH, 1995, pp. 187-192
7. Ishikawa, T., Yamamura, T., Hirokawa, T., Hayashi, Y., Noguchi, Y., and Matsushima, M., "Strength and fracture toughness properties of oxidation resistant high-temperature ceramic matrix composites", *Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Composite Materials: Volume II (A. Miravette, Ed.)*, Woodhead Publishing Co., Madrid, 1993, pp. 137-144.
8. Davies, I. J., Ishikawa, T., Shibuya, M., and Hirokawa, T., "Stress/strain behavior of 3-D woven SiC/SiC-based composites", submitted to *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, 1996
9. "Advanced technical ceramics - Mechanical properties of ceramic composites at room temperature. Part 1: Determination of tensile strength", Report no. DD ENV 658-1, British Standards, Manchester, U.K., March 1993
10. A. G. Evans, "Perspective on the development of high toughness ceramics", *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 73, 1990, pp. 187-206
11. Davies, I. J., Ishikawa, T., Shibuya, M., Hirokawa, T., "Optical microscopy of 3-D woven SiC/SiC-based composites", submitted to *Composites Science and Technology*, 1996

12. Davies, I. J., Ishikawa, T., Shibuya, M., and Hirokawa, T., "Fibre properties in 3-D woven SiC/SiC-based composites after tensile testing at room and elevated temperature", *in preparation*
13. Droillard, C. and Lamon, J., "Fracture toughness of 2-D woven SiC/SiC CVI-composites with multilayered interphases", *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 79, No. 4, 1996, pp. 849-858
14. Prewo, K., "Tension and flexure strength of silicon carbide fibre-reinforced glass-ceramics", *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 21, 1986, pp. 3590
15. Emig, G. and Wirth, R., "Tensile strength of silicon carbide fibre bundles at elevated temperatures", *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 30, 1995, pp. 5813-5818
16. Thouless, M. D., Sbaizero, O., Sigl, L. S., and Evans, A. G., "Effect of interface mechanical properties on pullout in a SiC-fiber-reinforced lithium aluminium silicate glass-ceramic", *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 72, No. 4, 1989, pp. 525-532
17. Davies, I. J., Ishikawa, T., Shibuya, M., and Hirokawa, T., "Damage characterisation of 3-D woven SiC/SiC-based composites", *Proceedings of the 21st Symposium on Composite Materials (Oct. 31st-Nov. 1st 1996, Toyama, Japan)*, Japan Society for Composite Materials, Tokyo, 1996, pp. 103-104
18. Eckel, A. J., and Bradt, R. C., "Strength distribution of reinforcing fibres in a Nicalon fiber/chemically vapor infiltrated silicon carbide matrix composite", *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 72, No. 3, 1989, pp. 455-458
19. Naslain, R., "The concept of layered interphases in SiC/SiC", *High-Temperature Ceramic-Matrix Composites II (A. G. Evans and R. Naslain, Ed.)*, *Ceramic Transactions volume 58*, American Ceramic Society, Westerville, OH, 1995, pp. 23-39